

FEATURES OF WITHDRAWAL OF HYPOTHYROIDISM IN THE CLIMACTERIC PERIOD AMONG RESIDENTS OF THE ALAT DISTRICT

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Relevance of the topic: by 2020, the incidence of thyroid disease in the world is 30%. Primary hypothyroidism in adults among thyroid disorders was 65% as of 2017 [Noddelman, 2017, Rosstat]. Our thyroid function is studied in different populations.

The inverse relationship between TTH and age iodine deficit is observed in populations, where the most common thyroid pathology is the presence of nodules and the function of the thyroid gland increases with age.

Today, menopausal women make up 10% of the world's population.

Of these, 10-75% of women have a pathological climacteric period [Sandakova E.A., Elkin.VD., Kobernik.M.Yu.2013].

It is characterized by an increase in TTH levels in hypothyroidism and can be active from subclinical or clinical.

Objective: to study the health of women in the climacteric period of the population of the Alat district.

Research materials and methods: in a retrospective method, 75 patients registered with the Alat District Central Polyclinic of the Bukhara region were identified. Patients are divided into 3 groups by age: premenopausal, menopausal and postmenopausal. All women were surveyed for TTH, free T4, thyroid ultrasound, thyroid palpation, body mass index, joint swelling, skin, muscle tone examination, mood swings, memory impairment. Attention, decreased sex potential, sleeping disorders or difficulty sleeping, weakness, fatigue, feeling sleepy, depression.

Research results: A survey of women of fertile and climacteric age found the following symptoms: weakness-30%. anxiety -25%, sleep disorders or difficulty falling asleep-40%, decreased sex drive-5%. Examination of women found: dry skin - 45 %, swelling of the limbs-15 %, decreased muscle tone- 5% , constipation - 30%. When determining the body mass index: overweight - 20%, L-level obesity - 43 %,2-level obesity - 27 %,3-level obesity - 10%. When palpating the thyroid gland, 50% of women were found to have an enlarged thyroid 1st degree ,2 nd degrees -35%, 3 rd degrees-15%.

Ultrasound of the thyroid gland - hyperplasia of the thyroid gland has increased in all women of fertile age, since they are listed by endocrinologists on various diseases. The laboratory conclusions are as follows: TTH-5-10 mIU/ml-51 %, 10-15 mIU/ml-36 %, 16 mIU/ml -13%.

Conclusion:

1. The health of women of climacteric age, residents of the Alat district, requires close attention, since it is during this period that many hormonal changes occur, which in turn lead to pathological changes in women's health.

2. In order to prevent the development of hypothyroidism in women of the menopausal period, it is advisable to prevent diseases in the pre-menopausal period.

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